

IRAN YESTERDAY, TODAY AND TOMORROW

ULUGBEK KHOLBEKOV ABDULLAJONOVICH

Teaching assistant at Andijan State Technical University, Andijan, Uzbekistan

ALISHER SOTVOLDIYEV ABDUMUXTAROVICH

PhD at Andijan State Technical University, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

Information and logic have always shaped our understanding of the world. Today, science helps us face complex challenges and guides us toward a more enlightened future. Real strength lies in bringing together knowledge from different disciplines. Great writers like Robert Kiyosaki emerge from discipline, experience, and courage. Raised in a hard-working Japanese family, he was unafraid to speak honestly about societies — including Muslim-majority communities — where work ethic and values remain strong. His ideas matter because they challenge comfort and awaken awareness.

“On June 22, 2025, The United States Air Force and Navy attacked three nuclear facilities in Iran, under the code name Operation Midnight Hammer. This Is How Modern Conflict Actually Starts. Wars today don’t begin with bombs. They begin with money.” - Robert Kiyosaki.

“The pattern is always the same:

- A country becomes financially isolated
- Sanctions restrict trade
- Currency collapses under inflation
- Foreign reserves dry up
- Energy exports become political
- Payment systems turn into weapons”

Middle Eastern countries always have two problems that attracts international players such as the USA and the UN. First, Elections, their long serving presidents and second, supporting the war-maker in the war such as Syria and Russia. Their destiny could have reached a different path though when they cooperated with the USA. At first, it would not occurred to them, only what they had done in their politics were to become less active in international matters, because if the country do not lead thus it is not led like neutral countries such as Central Asia and Switzerland. For example, Iran is always helping the war-maker side such as supporting Syrian president and recently assisting Russia. We are used to the idea that economies just keep growing year on year with occasional blips, but that we become richer all the time. But that hasn’t always been the case. Good old times may have been old, but they weren’t good. The vast bulk of people lived in Middle Eastern countries (like Iran) lived on the brink of famine, disease, death, and misery. Now they are living in a world that is radically different and the question is how did they become that way and so there is more to than one answer to that but the answer we will focus on is that we have been accumulating something which I call useful knowledge which is sort of a compilation of science (game theory) and information (regression methods). When someone looks at how elective destruction fuels growth or discourages if there is none, they have to look at the long run growth. Long run growth is driven by cumulative disruptive elections where each elected candidate stands on giant shoulders. We build on economies by work of previous presidents. Over the last two decades, the Middle Eastern countries have seen stagnated economic growth. Due to long serving presidents and absence of elective disruptions in their elections that are essential to further progress. Elective destruction when new presidents displace former presidents on time. This process of elective destruction creates conflict that must be managed. Because, the path of former presidents will be blocked and is put under threat by new elections and candidates. If elective disruptions are to succeed one another in a self-generating process, we need not only to know that something works, but also why. Question is, can Middle Eastern countries grow without limit? What about the finite resources. At some point they have also to modify this growth

EUROPEAN UNION & USA		fail from presidential election	do not fail and get elected again
		\$ 773.62 millions	\$ 639.36 millions
Fail from presidential elections		\$6,217 billions	\$6,217 billions
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We know that two candidates, former President and its opponent, have only two political options for being elected: fail and get elected next time or re-elected again. If former presidents agree to work together with its people and fail one time and get elected next time, and both sides will gain international recognition and gain \$773.62 million (21 percent more than previous year) Iran in 2026, or 6.217 billions of dollars European Union and USA combined. As in the Nash equation, the following situation, known as the prisoner’s dilemma, assumes that both sides lose if they act separately without international cooperation and limitations on their people’s freedom of will. It is clear that they can switch policies. The involvement of the presidents are so important that if both sides reach mutual agreement, this bad outcome can be avoided.

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